

Studies on the Dye-Humus Acids Complex

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The interaction between humus acids and six different dyes has been studied. It is found that methylene blue, acriflavine and rhodamine B bind to humus while rhodamine 6G, crystal violet and acridine yellow do not. This is due to an acid-base type interaction between the dye cation and humate anion.

ORGANIC cations such as dyes, quaternary ammonium compounds etc., are found to take part in exchange reactions on and from the certain adsorbent surfaces such as agar, gelatin, clays etc.¹⁻⁷

The studies on the dye-polymer interaction have been proved to be an important technique in the elucidation and structural and conformational aspects of long chain homo and heteropolymers. Moreover, the studies also reveal much informations regarding active sites and biological activities of the macromolecules. Humus substances are macromolecules in nature. The exchange reactions of humus acids with metallic cations have been studied in details^{8,9,10}. But no study has yet been done on dye-humus interaction. The present work deals with this study with a view to understanding how dyes interact with humus acids and their mode of binding.

Experimental

For the present work six different dyes have been chosen. They are methylene blue, acridine yellow, rhodamine 6G, rhodamine B, crystal violet and acriflavine. Humus was extracted from Dehradun soil by 0.5N Na₂CO₃ solution and fractionated to humic and fulvic acids by the method described earlier¹¹. Humic acid was converted to Na-form by adding dilute NaOH solution to pH 7 and dried under vacuum. Fulvic acid being soluble in aqueous solution was used as such.

The concentration of Na-humate and fulvic acid solutions was 0.0043% and the concentration of the solution of dyes was in the order of 10⁻⁵M for methylene blue, rhodamine 6G, rhodamine B, crystal violet and acridine yellow and for acriflavine it was in the order of 10⁻⁴M. Dyes and Na-humate and fulvic acid solutions were mixed in 1:1 proportion (V/V) and their O.D.s' at different wavelengths were measured with the help of a Carl Zeiss spectrophotometer.

Results and Discussion

Humic substances adsorb over the whole range of spectrum, the absorption increasing with decreasing wavelength. Thus the absorption curve is monotonic having no maximum or minima in the measurable range. To such a solution if a dye having its characteristic maxima in the visible range is added, it is expected that, if there is no interaction or binding, the absorption curve of this resultant mixture will be simple algebraic sum of the absorption spectra of the two entities in the low concentration range where no other interaction complicates the situation. In other words at each wavelength.

O.D. of dye humus mixture—

O.D. of humus = O.D. of the dye.

Fig. 1.

○—Pure Methylene Blue
●—M.B. + Na-Humate (1:1)

The above equality will not be valid if there is interaction between the two. Curves drawn in the above manner are shown in Figs. 1 and 2 (curves of fulvic acid with dyes being similar with that of Na-humate and dyes were omitted). It is evident that M.B., acriflavine and rhodamine B bind to humus while rhodamine 6G, crystal violet and acridine

yellow do not. Although all the dyes studied are cationic, preferential binding of some rather than all is very striking. This can be explained in terms of an acid base type interaction between the dye cation and humate anion. It is noteworthy that only those dyes having quaternary nitrogen cation with less electrophilic character binds humic acids

Fig. 2.

○—Pure Acriflavine
●—Acriflavine + Na-Humate (1 : 1)

Fig. 3.

○—Pure Rhodamine B
●—Rhodamine B + Na-Humate (1 : 1)

Fig. A

better as per above criterion (Fig. A). It will be more clear by considering two similar pair of dyes viz., (a) rhodamine B and rhodamine 6G and (b) acriflavine and acridine yellow. They are discussed below :

- (a) Rhodamine B binds while rhodamine 6G does not. If we represent dye cation in these case as DR^+ where $R = H$ for rhodamine 6G and $R = C_2H_5$ for rhodamine B and humate anion as A^- then dye-humus equilibrium will be

when $R = H$ in case of rhodamine 6G

A careful consideration of resonating structures of the dye cations (Fig. A) contributing to their colour will show that the above interactions do not any way modify them. Moreover, above interaction being coulombic and very weak (particularly in aqueous solution) does not influence the symmetry of the original dye cations so that no discernable peak shift is observed. But it is sufficient to cause a broadening and lowering of intensity of the dye-cation

spectra. In the case of rhodamine 6G, this weak interaction is further weakened by the equilibrium (2), since here dye cation can cause a proton transfer to the polymer anion and hence the spectra of the mixture is an algebraic sum of the two entities D and HA.

- (b) The same type of argument holds good for the pair acriflavine and acridine yellow. Only here the active site *i.e.*, quaternary nitrogen being involved in a ring system, a higher concentration of dye is required to get an observable effect.

The above acid base type interaction is also observed with triphenyl methane dyes. Thus malachite green or crystal violet solution show the following reaction :

The same reaction is brought about by Na-humate solution instead of alkali.

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